

1 **The transcriptional response to HCV infection.**

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6 We studied the cellular response to HCV infection by measuring total transcription by RNA-sequencing in
7 human cells in a Huh7.5 hepatitis culture system. We demonstrate here activation of the UL16 binding
8 protein *ULBP1* in cells infected with HCV.

9 Citations

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